

2014

ISSN 2278-5655

Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ)

(Bi-Monthly)

Peer-Reviewed Journal

Impact factor:0.948

Aug-Sep Issues

Chief-Editor

Ubale Amol Baban

***PEER-REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL***

[Editorial/Head Office: 108, Gokuldharm Society, Dr.Ambedkar chowk, Near
TV Towar,Badlapur, MS

**INNOVATIVE BEST PRACTICES IN MAHTMA PHULE A.S. COLLEGE LIBRARY
PANVEL DIST-RAIGAD (M.S.) INDIA**

Library Science

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Abstract :

This paper presents a case study of enhancing user connect by applying best practices in the Mahatma Phule A.S.C.College , Central Library. Central Library is the place of support for the entire range of academic activities on the college campus. In today's ICT environment, library support has made available by applying various best practices to fulfill the needs of the users in vast range. Computerization of the college library is completed in preplanned systematic way, process and systems. The library services has been expanded by making available more services stations to students and faculty with open access for PG students and faculty. As various levels of students are coming in reading room, token system is applied to enhancing reading habits in the student community. The College, Central library has achieved best success and attraction to students community by these best practices. The aim of this study is to present the best services made available to users by the College, Central library.

Key Words: *Best practices, Library Computerization, Circulation, Reading Room.*

Introduction

The best practices are the improvement in the conventional practices to service accessible practices. In the dynamic age, each and every institute should improve their services to the customer centered and oriented. The high quality output can take place by application of best practices in the institution. The library is the important academic supporting center in the higher education institute. It should apply the best practices to serve highly their users as per their local

environment. The College Central Library has established some best practices like, systems, processes and methods of library computerization increase in number of service stations in the library and token system to students for reading rooms.

The theme ‘Process’- The Wikipedia defines it as:

A process involves steps & decisions in the way work is accomplished & may involve a sequence of event. The process that one follows is as important as the results that are produced by the process. Without understanding the underlying process, it is difficult to know how a certain set of results were achieved or why they were good or bad.

Best Practices Meaning &Definition:

According to Wikipedia, best practices are commonly used where no specific formal methodology is in place or the existing methodology does not sufficiently address the issue. The idea is that with proper processes, checks & testing a desired outcome can be delivered more effectively with fewer problems and unforeseen complications. In addition a “best” practice can evolve to become better as improvements are discovered.

If one thinks with an open creative mind, in almost every aspect of library a range of best practices can be evolved.

Computerization process & increasing service stations having large users in the library are assets of any library, especially in college library. Best practices are nothing but the increasing maximum use of the available resources & delighting the users.

ICT enabled Library Services

For the Libraries, ICT’s has tremendously changed the Management of Resources or House Keeping Operations as well as the way services are delivered. While general IT application tools and Integrated Library Management Systems are largely used in housekeeping operations, like acquisition, cataloguing, circulation control, serials control etc. Use of ICT in the library saves the time of library staff and users, energy and increases accuracy and speed in the work. Library computerization is the basic mean in the application of ICT.

Library Computerization:

College Central Library has started computerization process on July 1, 2010 with the

installation of the MKCL's (Pune) Libreria: Library Management system. LIBRERIA windows & client based software. The data entry of text books was made complete within three months of the period from software installation with bar-coding. There were used ten stations to complete the data entry work of the text books.

Bar-Coding & Marking Label:

Bar-coding and computerized marking label pasting work on the back of the book was completed on the same date of data entry. This system was decided at the time of library computerization planning.

Human Resource

Human resource was used from the professionally trained B. Lib., M. Lib. & other college students under earn & learn scheme. This scheme was run by the college for financial help to students' for their education. They had given complete training of the library computerization process by the Librarian.

Student's membership and circulation

By completing data entry work of the text books, library has made available circulation with computerized environment using bar-code of the books. Student's membership data entry work was completed immediate after completing text books data entry work.

Reference Books Data Entry:

Reference books data entry process was started after starting text books circulation to the students with computerized system. It was decided that to made data entry of reference books by subject wise. There are more courses in the subject of chemistry up to M.Sc. level, we had given preference to chemistry reference books in first stage. It was completed with bar-coding within fifteen days. The chemistry reference books were ready for circulation to concern students & faculty.

Faculty Membership Botany Department:

Faculty membership of the Botany subject was completed immediately with filling their membership forms.

Computerized of circulation for faculty :

Computerized circulation to faculty of Botany & students was started with bar-code scanner. At this stage previous circulation on register to faculty was stopped of the concern faculty. Data entry of the books issued on the register was made from the accession register and these accession numbers were taken on the account of concern faculty through computerized system.

Circulation Stations:

Two circulation stations were made available to students & faculty. One was for books issuing & another one was for return of books.

Data entry of other subject reference books & membership:

By this way data entry of other subject reference books & concerned subject faculty membership was completed continuously. Computerized circulation of concern subject books to students & faculty was started with barcode scanners.

Demand of Un-computerized Books:

Meanwhile demand of un-computerized books was made by the faculty & students. This problem was solved by doing data entry of the same demanded reference books day-to-day. Whenever it was not possible to do data entry at the same day it was done to second day & made available these reference books for circulation.

Library Service Stations:

An academic library has to provide library users with dynamic equipment, facilities, Resources and services to support their learning activities, Keeping this view library has made available more access from the library through establishing various service stations.

Library Buildings & Sections:

Central library has two floored separate beautiful building at the central place of the college campus, which enables easy access to the students & faculty. There was a circulation counter, Research reference Section, Book Processing & Reprography, Librarian Cabin, Text books room, stack room for science & commerce reference books sections at ground floor. At first floor there were separate boys' & girls' reading rooms & Internet section for faculty & student.

There was more than six thousand student's strength of the college every year with junior, senior & Post Graduate levels. There were arts, commerce, science, management, information technology streams.

There was crowded circumstance at the circulation counter regularly in the library. The library had decided to extend three more counters for circulation, without destroying the previous counter status at ground floor.

Management of the additional new counters:

Three additional new counters were made by destroying unusable two walls at the counter. There was prepared one for books issuing, one for book return for the students & another one for faculty & staff circulation at the ground floor. One additional counter was prepared at first floor to reading room service.

Now there are four library service stations at ground floor & one at first floor. The extension of service stations, students & faculty are getting more access to the library & it saves the time & energy. Various service stations are avoiding the crowd at one place. It helps to provide accurate and more access to the library. It becomes more attraction to the library with giving right to the information to users. This arrangement of extending library service stations is the best practice in the library.

Book Bank facility on ¼ Price :

Through this scheme whole set of books is made available to student on ¼ price for whole year.

Scholar Card to merit us students :

Additional membership card is provided to scholar those who stood first in each class is provided to encourage their interest towards reading habit.

Reading Hall Services:

There are two reading rooms separately for boys and girls students. Books are issued to students for their study to one day. They are mandatory to return on the same day. Our experience was students are gathering in a place and making noise in the reading room. It was unhealthy to other students to study in the reading room.

Token System for Reading Room:

The library had studied the situation and decided to use of tokens for students in reading room. The round plastic tokens were purchased in two colors and they have given numbers from one to sixty for boys and same for girls students. Seat numbers in the reading rooms were also allotted as token numbers. When students came to use the reading room, there was system to take the ID card of the student and issue him a token for entering in the reading room. It was mandatory to seat at the concern seat number as per issued token. Checking was made regularly after some time. After leaving the reading room, students were supposed to submit the token and collect their ID card. This token system has given grand success in the reading room for their best study with silent environment.

Conclusion:

The maximum use of library in the ICT age should be happened with their resources. Various types of best practices are using the libraries for best services to users. MPASC College Central Library has taken initiatives by adopting some innovative best practices in the library. The Central Library has adopted best practices like Computerization systems, process and methods, management of more circulation stations and token system for reading room. It has made extensive use and access to the library by users.

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